

cel 3/4

immun

PRKT

PKT

total

lysate

Gel 3/4

15pc

p-ANT

ART

5/2d'

b-ant

ANT

4/2

Phospho blot

T

REC1

1

GAPDH

T

T

Fam 1012 Blot
total blot
Setz

Setz Akt + 56 blot Erk blot
55er total blot gel 44

